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THE EFFECT OF ORGANIZATIONAL SUPPORT ON EMPLOYEE CREATIVITY: MODERATING ROLES OF TRUST IN ORGANIZATION AND PSYCHOLOGICAL OWNERSHIP

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ABSTRACT

This study aims to investigate the relationship between Perceived Organizational Support (POS) and Employee Creative Behavior (ECB), focusing on the moderating roles of Trust in Organization (TiO) and Psychological Ownership (PO). The survey study of 409 employees from Turkish companies conducted in 2023 uses Exploratory factor analysis (EFA), correlation analysis, regression analysis, and PROCESS Model 1 to test direct and moderation hypotheses. The results confirm a direct positive relationship between POS and ECB, emphasizing the critical role of organizational support in fostering employee creativity. Additionally, TiO and PO significantly moderate this relationship, with higher levels of trust and ownership amplifying the effect of POS on ECB. Although the study is limited by its cross-sectional design and geographic focus on Turkey, it provides valuable insights into the mechanisms that drive creativity in organizations, offering a more nuanced understanding of how support, trust, and ownership interact to promote creative behaviors. The findings suggest that organizational leaders should focus not only on providing support but also on cultivating a high-trust environment and fostering a sense of psychological ownership among employees to maximize creativity. This study fills a gap in psychology and management literature by examining the relationship between POS and ECB, emphasizing the crucial roles of trust and ownership as moderators in fostering employee creativity. It also explores these dynamics within the context of a developing country, specifically Turkey, to enhance the generalizability of POS-ECB findings.

KEYWORDS: Perceived Organizational Support, Employee Creative Behavior, Trust in Organization, Psychological Ownership.

1. INTRODUCTION

Employee Creative Behavior (ECB) has long attracted the interest of both researchers and practitioners. Defined as the generation of novel and valuable ideas for organizational improvement and adaptability, ECB is considered a core employee capacity in organizations that acknowledge the role of creativity in gaining competitive advantage (Amabile, 1988; Choi, 2007; Zhang & Zhou, 2014). In practice, organizations seek ways to support employees and unlock their creative potential to cope with rapidly changing marketplace demands (Scott & Bruce, 1994; Amabile, 1988; Mehmood, 2016; Suifan et al., 2018). Perceived Organizational Support (POS) employees' perception of the extent to which their contributions and well-being are valued—has emerged as a key antecedent of creativity. According to Blau's (1964) Social Exchange Theory (SET), when employees feel supported, they are more likely to reciprocate with positive work attitudes and behaviors (Eisenberger et al., 1986). Extant research confirms that POS enhances a wide range of outcomes, including job satisfaction, organizational commitment, innovative behavior, and job performance (Kamil & Nasurdin, 2016; Kuratko et al., 2014; Yousuf et al., 2022). Specifically, numerous studies demonstrate a positive POS–ECB link (Zhou & George, 2001; Tang et al., 2017; Duan et al., 2020), consistently reflecting the reciprocity principle of SET (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Singh et al., 2023). Despite this strong empirical foundation, limited research has examined how contextual and psychological factors shape the POS–ECB relationship. In particular, Trust in Organization (TiO) and Psychological Ownership (PO) may moderate the extent to which POS translates into creativity, yet these moderators remain underexplored. Moreover, much of the existing research has been conducted in developed economies such as China, the United Kingdom, or South Korea, with relatively little attention to developing country contexts. This study aims to fill these gaps by re-examining the POS–ECB relationship in the context of a developing country. By investigating TiO and PO as moderators, the study provides a more comprehensive understanding of the conditions that strengthen or weaken the creative outcomes of organizational support. Considering that organizational dynamics and employee perceptions in developing countries may differ from those in developed economies, this approach enhances both the theoretical contribution and practical relevance of the findings. The paper is structured as follows: First, the existing literature is reviewed, and three related

hypotheses are developed. Second, the research methodology is explained, including sample selection, measures, and data analysis procedures. Third, the results of the hypothesis tests are presented and interpreted. Finally, the study's findings, contributions, limitations, and directions for future research are discussed.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW AND HYPOTHESIS

2.1. *Perceived Organizational Support (POS)*

Social Exchange Theory (SET) formulated by Blau (1964) posits that employees who perceive a supportive organizational climate feel grateful to reciprocate with constructive intentions and beneficial reactions to their organization (Rivai et al., 2019; Alpkhan et al., 2021). When employees sense organizational backing, their commitment to the organization's welfare and objectives intensifies and they exhibit positive attitudes and behaviors in response (Rhoades & Eisenberger, 2002; Kamil & Nasurdin, 2016). In this concern, POS—encapsulating employees' beliefs that the organization values their input and is concerned about their overall welfare, make them more inclined to respond with favorable work attitudes and conduct (Eisenberger et al., 1986; Eisenberg et al., 2020). Employees discern organizational support through various organizational evaluations, encompassing praise, recognition, rewards like compensation, promotion, job enrichment, and organizational practices (Kim et al., 2004). Kuratko et al. (2014) identified five crucial dimensions determining a supportive environment: top management support, work discretion/autonomy, rewards/reinforcement, time availability, and organizational boundaries. Besides, from a broader point of view, the greater the management support in organizations, the higher their innovative performance (e.g. Alpkhan et al., 2010).

2.2. *Employee Creative Behavior (ECB)*

ECB is the process of generating and implementing new and valuable ideas in the workplace, playing a crucial role in an organization's ability to adapt and respond to changing demands (Scott & Bruce, 1994). Organizations that proactively support and cultivate creativity among their workforce often find themselves at a competitive edge, better equipped to navigate swiftly changing market conditions (Amabile, 1988). Organizations are increasingly viewing employee creativity as a critical driver of competitive advantage. It empowers employees to enhance organizational performance

and explore novel processes, methods, or products (Akgunduz et al., 2018), thereby securing long-term viability and distinct competitive positioning (Mehmood, 2016) and promoting sustainability (Suifan et al., 2018). Moreover, creative ideas resolving problems and fostering practical solutions to workplace challenges are very vital for organizational development and success and they can originate from employees at any organizational level and in any job role (Shalley et al., 2004; Zhou et al., 2011; Zhang & Zhou, 2014).

2.3. POS and ECB Relationship

Creatively inclined employees often need to navigate organizational red tape and advocate persistently for their ideas to secure managerial backing and the freedom to explore them (Caniëls & Rietzschel, 2015). In this concern, supervisors' support enhances employees' work engagement and promotes creative behaviors (Appu & Sia, 2015). Moreover, the role of leadership is essential. Studies indicate that ambidextrous leadership—balancing support for novel ideas with structured guidance—can significantly foster creative tendencies by providing both the freedom to explore and the stability needed to implement ideas (Akıncı & Alpan, 2022). Furthermore, research underscores that leadership styles emphasizing authenticity and employee development, such as servant and transformational leadership, create an environment where employees feel safe to engage in creative behaviors, thereby enhancing innovative thinking (Ucar et al., 2021b). Therefore, POS is needed to minimize the risks associated with creativity, to believe that creative ideas will be practical, and to boost the likelihood of creative efforts among employees accordingly (Zhou & George, 2001). Likewise, employees with positive moods conducive to creativity engage in communication and interaction, gaining access to more information and ideas and participating in creative processes, all leading to greater creative output (Zhang et al., 2016; Tang et al., 2017). Therefore, we hypothesize that employees who perceive a higher degree of organizational support are likelier to participate in creative behaviors.

H1. Perceived Organizational Support (POS) is positively related to Employee Creative Behavior (ECB).

2.4. Moderating Role of Trust in Organization (TiO)

An organization's care and concern for its employees' well-being convey its benevolence and

goodwill, enhances its perceived trustworthiness and indicates its commitment not to exploit employee vulnerabilities; then this contributes to the formation of a trustworthy organizational culture which is vital for safe and peaceful work environments (Chen et al., 2004; Eisenberg et al., 2020; Joo, et al., 2023). Positive employee expectations and beliefs about their organization being competent, benevolent, honest, predictable and reliable facilitate employee confidence to turn into action with creative undertakings especially when support is needed (Shockley-Zalabak et al. 2000; Rhoades et al., 2001; Özyılmaz et al., 2018). Trust, as a sense of corporate identity, and a commitment to long-term obligations (Akkoç & Yılmaz, 2019) is a crucial element of social exchange, explaining how employees develop positive attitudes towards their organization and positive behaviors in return. Creative behaviors are among them since trust is a critical component of a creative climate (e.g. Barsh et al. 2008; Jo and Lee, 2012; Jiang & Chen, 2016; Rodrigues & Veloso, 2013). Employees with high levels of trust are likelier to take risks for the organization's benefit without fearing negative consequences (Neves & Eisenberger, 2014). Moreover, employees are more inclined to propose creative ideas and suggestions when they perceive their organizations as highly supportive, fostering a sense of trust and confidence (Tang et al., 2017). In this concern, the interplay between POS and TiO is also critical by mutually strengthening their positive impacts. Employees can be much more motivated to put forth extra risky efforts to be able to contribute to organizational creativity and innovativeness -even if potentially harmful (e.g. Shateri & Hayat, 2020) if they have in mind a positive perception of being supported by their organization together with a trustworthy attitude at the same time towards this organization. Based on these insights, we propose that TiO moderates the relationship between POS and ECB. A high level of trust amplifies the positive effects of perceived support on creative behavior, emphasizing the significance of a trustworthy organizational environment in facilitating employee creativity. Therefore, we hypothesize that:

H2. Trust in Organization (TiO) moderates the relationship between Perceived Organizational Support (POS) and Employee Creative Behavior (ECB).

2.5. Moderating Role of Psychological Ownership (PO)

Psychological ownership (PO) is defined by Pierce et al. (2001) as a subjective feeling of "owning" the organization, which may not necessarily involve

legal ownership but answers the question, “What do I perceive as mine?” This sense of ownership has been shown to foster positive attitudes and pro-organizational discretionary behaviors that benefit organizational functioning (Baer & Brown, 2012; Van Dyne & Pierce, 2004; Mayhew et al., 2007; Liu et al., 2012; Ramos et al., 2014).

Recent studies further indicate that PO is not only a vital driver of employees’ creative efforts, much like POS (Parks et al., 2010; Sözbilir, 2020), but also complements POS by strengthening employees’ psychological connection and dedication to their organization (McIntyre et al., 2009; Ötken, 2015; Nurtjahjani et al., 2021). For example, Ucar et al. (2021a) highlight that PO can enhance creative

behavior by reinforcing this emotional bond, thereby cultivating an environment conducive to innovation.

Considering this complementary relationship, we propose that PO positively moderates the POS-ECB link. In other words, when employees simultaneously perceive strong organizational support and feel psychological ownership, their creative behaviors are expected to be amplified.

H3. PO moderates the relationship between **2.6. Perceived Organizational Support (POS) and (ECB).**

The theoretical model is depicted in Figure 1 based on the suggested hypotheses.

Figure 1: Theoretical Model.

3. METHODOLOGY

3.1. Sample and Data Collection

This study employed a convenience sampling method to distribute the survey to 580 employees working in Turkish companies. Convenience sampling was selected due to the accessibility of participants and the feasibility of gathering data within a limited timeframe and resource constraints. While this method allows for efficient data collection, it may introduce potential biases, such as limiting the generalizability of the findings to a broader population. To mitigate these concerns, efforts were made to ensure that participants represented various sectors and job roles within their organizations. A total of 416 employees responded to the survey, and after data cleaning, 409 valid responses were included in the final analysis, resulting in a 72% response rate. By adhering to relevant ethical guidelines in Türkiye, we assured participants of the confidentiality of their responses, and informed consent was obtained from all participants during

the data collection process. The survey employed a five-point Likert scale ranging from "1: strongly disagree" to "5: strongly agree."

3.2. Measures

The constructs in this research were operationalized using reliable and valid scales previously published in high-quality peer-reviewed journals. All responses were assessed on a five-point Likert-type scale ranging from "1: strongly disagree" to "5: strongly agree".

3.2.1. Perceived Organizational Support (POS)

The widely used scale adapted from Kuratko et al. (1990; 1992) and Horsnby et al. (2002) will be employed to measure POS. This scale assesses employees' perceptions of the extent to which the Organization values their contributions and cares about their well-being. Sample items include "Employees from every level will be rewarded if they innovate." and "Upper management is aware and very receptive to ideas and suggestions."

3.2.2. *Employee Creative Behavior (ECB)*

Creative behavior will be assessed using a validated scale derived from George & Zhou's (2001) and Tierney et al. (1999) work, capturing employees' self-reported engagement in novel and valuable work-related ideas. Sample items are "Suggests new ways to achieve goals or objectives" and "Exhibits creativity on the job when given the opportunity to."

3.2.3. *Trust in Organization (TiO)*

Trust in Organization will be measured utilizing the scale developed by Robinson and Rousse (1994). This scale evaluates employees' beliefs in the Organization's credibility, benevolence, and integrity. A sample item is "I believe my employer has high integrity" and "My employer is open and upfront with me."

3.2.4. *Psychological Ownership (PO)*

The measure for Psychological Ownership will be adapted from Dyne & Pierce (2004), focusing on individuals' sense of possession and connection with their work. Measurement items include, "This is MY Organization, I sense that this Organization is OUR company.", and "This is OUR company."

To ensure the reliability and validity of the scales used in the study, Cronbach's alpha was calculated for each scale to assess internal consistency. All scales exceeded the commonly accepted threshold of 0.70 for Cronbach's alpha, indicating internal solid reliability. Additionally, exploratory factor analysis (EFA) was conducted to confirm the construct validity of the scales.

3.3. *Data Analysis*

The collected data were analyzed using SPSS and PROCESS Macro (Hayes, 2012). Several steps were followed to ensure the robustness and clarity of the findings:

3.3.1. *Descriptive Statistics*

Including age, gender, sector, and years of experience, were computed to characterize the sample.

Correlation Analysis was conducted to explore the initial relationships between POS, ECB, TiO, and PO. This allowed us to examine how these variables were related before conducting more advanced analyses.

3.3.2. *Reliability and Validity Checks*

As mentioned earlier, the internal consistency of the scales was assessed through Cronbach's alpha,

and construct validity was examined through exploratory factor analysis (EFA). These steps ensured the reliability and validity of the measures used in the study.

3.3.3. *Regression and Moderation Analysis*

Hierarchical regression analysis was used to test the proposed hypotheses. The primary focus was on moderation analysis to examine the moderating effects of Trust in Organization (TiO) and Psychological Ownership (PO) on the POS-ECB relationship. We utilized PROCESS Model 1 in the PROCESS Macro for SPSS (Hayes, 2012), which allows for the assessment of moderation effects by introducing interaction terms between the independent variable (POS) and the moderators (TiO and PO) in the regression models.

The interaction terms were created by multiplying the standardized values of the independent variable (POS) and each moderator (TiO and PO). The significance of these interaction terms was then tested to determine whether TiO and PO significantly moderated the relationship between POS and ECB. The analysis controlled for relevant demographic variables (e.g., age, gender, and years of experience) to ensure that the findings were robust and not confounded by these factors. PROCESS Model 1 was selected for its ability to assess simple moderation, making it suitable for examining the impact of a single moderator on the relationship between an independent and dependent variable.

The moderation effects were visualized through interaction plots, where the relationship between POS and ECB was plotted at different levels of TiO and PO (e.g., low, medium, and high). This provided a clearer understanding of how the strength of the POS-ECB relationship changes at varying levels of trust and ownership within the organization.

Additionally, given the self-reported survey design, common method bias (CMB) was considered. Although a separate Harman's single-factor test was not formally conducted, the first factor in the exploratory factor analysis explained approximately 30–40% of the variance, which is below the recommended 50% threshold.

3.4. *Findings*

The statistical analyses conducted in this study yield significant findings, corroborating all three proposed hypotheses related to the impact of Perceived Organizational Support (POS) on Employee Creative Behavior (ECB) and the moderating roles of Trust in Organization (TiO) and Psychological Ownership (PO).

3.4.1. Descriptive Statistics

This research encompassed a diverse sample of 409 participants to examine organizational dynamics. As seen in Table 1, gender distribution within the sample was predominantly male, constituting 61.4%, while females represented 38.6%. Regarding age, most participants fell within the 30-40 year age range, accounting for 46% of the sample, suggesting that the study primarily captured the perspectives of mid-career professionals.

Educational attainment among participants was notably high, with 56.3% holding a Bachelor's degree and 40.3% possessing a Master's degree. A small fraction, 3.4%, reported having a PhD degree. Work

experience varied, with a significant majority of 74.6% having 0-15 years of experience. The remaining 25.4% of participants had 15 or more years of experience.

The organization size of participants was also diverse. Small organizations with 10-100 employees comprised 20.5% of the sample. Medium-sized organizations with 100-1000 employees accounted for 26%, and large organizations with over 1000 represented the most at 53.5%.

This demographic diversity strengthens the generalizability of the results across different organizational contexts, providing a broader understanding of how POS influences ECB in various settings.

Table 1: Statistical Description of the Research Sample.

Sample Characteristics		Sample (n=409)	Percentage (%)
Gender	Male	251	61,4
	Female	158	38,6
Age	20-30 years	144	35,2
	30-40 years	188	46
	40 years and above	77	18,8
Education	Bachelor's Degree	230	56,3
	Master's Degree	165	40,3
	PhD Degree	14	3,4
Work experience	0-15 years	305	74,6
	15 years and above	104	25,4
Organization Size	10-100 employees	84	20,5
	100-1000 employees	106	26
	1000 employees and above	219	53,5

4. MEASUREMENT MODEL ASSESSMENT AND CORRELATION RESULTS

As illustrated in Table 2, For the Perceived Organizational Support (POS) construct comprising 19 items, the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) was 0.521, suggesting that over half the variance observed in the items can be attributed to the construct they are intended to measure. The Composite Reliability (CR) score of 0.953 and Cronbach's Alpha of 0.932 exceed the accepted threshold of 0.7, indicating excellent internal consistency.

The Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) measure of sampling adequacy was 0.931, well above the commonly recommended value of 0.6, telling that the sample was sufficient for the analysis.

The Employee Creative Behavior (ECB) scale, with 15 items, showed an AVE of 0.478, a CR of 0.931, and a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.933, all pointing to high reliability. The KMO measure for ECB was an impressive 0.95, further supporting the scale's construct validity and the appropriateness of the

factor analysis.

Trust in Organization (TiO) and Psychological Ownership (PO) comprised 7 items each. TiO exhibited a strong AVE of 0.739, a CR of 0.952, and a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.941, while PO demonstrated similar robustness with an AVE of 0.737, a CR of 0.951 and a Cronbach's Alpha of 0.94.

These figures underscore the reliability and validity of the measures for these constructs, with KMO values of 0.921 and 0.903, respectively.

Eventually, the scales used in this study to measure the constructs (POS, ECB, TiO, PO) indicate high reliability and validity, as evidenced by the AVE, CR, Cronbach's Alpha, and KMO values affirming the robustness and strength of operationalization. As seen in Table 3, all of the constructs are significantly correlated to each other. The mean of PO is relatively low, and its standard deviation is relatively high, while ECB's mean is high.

Table 2: Reliability and Validity of Scale.

Construct	Number of Items	AVE	CR	Cronbach's Alpha	KMO
Perceived Organizational Support (POS)	19	0,521	0,953	0,932	0,931
Employee Creative Behavior (ECB)	15	0,478	0,931	0,933	0,95
Trust in Organization (TiO)	7	0,739	0,952	0,941	0,921
Psychological ownership (PO)	7	0,737	0,951	0,94	0,903

Table 3: Mean, Standard Deviation, and Correlation Analysis.

	Construct	Mean	SD	1	2	3
1	ECB	4,069	0,512			
2	PO	3,205	1,043	0,192**		
3	TiO	3,773	0,85	0,211**	0,616**	
4	POS	3,308	0,698	0,165**	0,570**	0,637**

Notes: *** p<0,001, **p<0,05, *p<0,1

4.1. Hypothesis Tests

Results of the regression model on the relation of POS on ECB (see Table 4) reveal that the model is a good fit since the adjusted R Square value is 0,025, and the F-statistic is 11,331, statistically significant (p < 0,001). The standardized Beta coefficient of POS is 0,165 and significant, confirming that POS is a significant and positive driver of ECB. Therefore, H1 is supported.

Table 4: Test of POS - ECB Relation (Dependent Variable is ECB).

Independent Variables:	Unstandardized Beta Coefficients	Standardized Beta Coefficients	t	Sig.
(Constant)	3,669		30,247	0,000
POS	0,121	0,165	3,366	0,001
Adjusted R Square:	0,025	F value:	11,331	0,001

Results of the regression model (see Table 5) on the moderator role of TiO in the relation of POS on ECB reveal that the model fits the data well since the adjusted R Square value is 0.069, and the F-statistic is 9,938, statistically significant (p < 0.000). The interaction term (Int_1), representing the combined effect of POS and TiO on ECB, has a coefficient of 0,110, which is also significant (p = .002). This indicates that TiO moderates positively the POS-ECB relation. Figure 2 also depicts that when TiO either is at a low level (2,922) or at the mean level (3,773), there is not any significant positive relation of POS on ECB. However, when TiO is high (4,623), it turns positive and significant. The topmost line represents the category with TiO of 4,623 and has a positive slope, indicated by the equation $y=3.78+0.11*x$, suggesting that as POS increases, ECB also increases. The results imply that POS increases ECB when TiO

is high, and decreases it when TiO is low. Therefore, H2 is supported.

Table 5: Test of the moderator role of TiO in the POS - ECB Relation (Dependent Variable is ECB).

Independent Variables:	Beta Coefficients	Standard error	t	Sig.
(Constant)	4,778	,416	11,473	0,000
POS	-,397	,146	-2,713	0,007
TiO	-,215	,110	-1,958	0,051
Int_1 (POS* TiO)	,110	,035	3,123	0,002
Adjusted R Square:	0,069	F value:	9,938	0,000

Figure 2. Moderation effect of TiO on the POS-ECB relationship. The relationship becomes statistically significant and positive only at high levels of TiO ($\beta = 0.11, p < 0.01$; equation: $y = 3.78 + 0.11x$). Slopes at the mean and low levels of TiO are non-significant. Axes: X = POS, Y = ECB. Lines depict low (-1 SD), mean (M), and high (+1 SD) TiO.

Results of the regression model (see Table 6) on the moderator role of PO in the relation of POS on ECB reveal that the model fits the data well since the adjusted R Square value is 0.054, and the F-statistic is 7.662, statistically significant (p < 0.001). The interaction term (Int_1), representing the combined effect of POS and PO on ECB, has a coefficient of 0.070, which is also significant (p = 0.023). This shows that PO moderates positively the POS-ECB relation. Figure 3 also depicts that when PO is at a low level (2.162) there is not any significant relation of POS on

ECB. When PO is at the mean level (3.205), there is a positive slope but still non-significant. However, when PO is high (4.248), the slope turns strongly and significantly upward. The topmost line represents this category with PO of 4.248 with a positive slope, indicated by the equation $y = 3.65 + 0.14x$, suggesting that as POS increases, ECB also increases. The results imply that POS increases ECB when PO is high. Therefore, H3 is supported.

Table 6: Test of the moderator role of PO in the POS - ECB Relation (Dependent Variable is ECB).

Independent Variables:	Beta Coefficients	Standard error	t	Sig.
(Constant)	4,317	,319	13,536	0,000
POS	-,155	,103	-1,502	0,134
PO	-,157	,104	-1,509	0,132
Int_1 (POS * PO)	,070	,030	2,288	0,023
Adjusted R Square:	0,054	F value:	7,662	0,000

Figure 3: Moderation effect of PO on the POS-ECB relationship. The relationship is statistically significant and positive only at high levels of PO ($\beta = 0.14$, $p < 0.05$). Slopes at the mean and low levels of PO are non-significant.

5. DISCUSSION

5.1. Interpretation of Research Findings

This study's findings support all three hypotheses, contributing valuable insights into the dynamics of Perceived Organizational Support (POS), Employee Creative Behavior (ECB), and the roles of various moderating factors.

The confirmation of the first hypothesis, which posits a positive and significant relationship between POS and ECB, aligns with existing literature emphasizing the importance of organizational support in enhancing employee creativity

(Eisenberger et al., 1986; Scott & Bruce, 1994). This correlation underscores the critical role of perceived support in fostering an environment where creative behaviors are encouraged and nurtured. Organizations striving for innovation must recognize the value of cultivating a supportive culture that acknowledges and cares for employee contributions and well-being. Although the effect of POS on ECB is statistically significant, the explained variance for the baseline model remains modest ($\text{Adj. } R^2 = 0.025$; Table 4). This pattern is not unexpected given that creativity is a multidetermined outcome shaped by individual, relational, and contextual factors. Importantly, our moderation models indicate that the POS-ECB link is conditional rather than uniform: the inclusion of TiO and PO interactions improves overall model fit ($\text{Adj. } R^2 = 0.069$ and 0.054 in Tables 5 and 6, respectively), and the simple slopes are meaningful at high levels of trust and psychological ownership. These results suggest that organizational support constitutes a necessary but not sufficient condition for creativity; its influence is amplified when embedded in high-trust and high-ownership climates

The study's findings also highlight the significant moderating role of Trust in Organization (TiO) in the POS-ECB relationship. However, the impact of TiO is notably significant only when levels of organizational trust are high. This conditionality suggests that trust is a foundational element in the POS-ECB dynamic, resonating with theories that stress the importance of trust in organizational relationships and creative processes (Akkoç & Yılmaz, 2019; Eisenberg et al., 2020). This is also in line with a recent study of Turesky et al.'s (2020) finding that a high-trust environment is critical for virtual team performance. Therefore, organizations must provide support and cultivate a high-trust environment to realize the potential benefits their employees' creativity.

Similarly, the positive moderation by Psychological Ownership (PO) in the POS-ECB relationship, mainly when PO is high, reveals a complex interplay between organizational support and creativity. This finding extends the understanding of how psychological ownership can amplify the effects of organizational support on creativity, especially within a trusting environment. It suggests that when employees feel a sense of ownership and are in a trusting context, their creative potentials are maximized (Pierce et al., 2001; Liu et al., 2012). This has significant implications for organizational practices, emphasizing the need to foster a sense of support and a sense of belonging and

ownership among employees.

5.2. Theoretical and Practical Implications

Theoretically, this study contributes to the organizational behavior literature by adding two moderators i.e. TiO and PO to our understanding of reciprocity in the relationship between perceptions (POS) and behaviors (ECB). The moderation of TiO strengthens the social exchange in such a way that employees who have already trusted in their organization behave more creatively when they feel supported. Similarly, the same applies to PO: those employees who adopt the company as their own behave more creatively when they feel supported. This implies that the social exchange between good perceptions and good reciprocations can be strengthened if employees have already developed positive attitudes and feelings like trust and ownership. Therefore the POS-ECB relation is not a straightforward process but it needs to be supported by the moderations of TiO and PO. From a practical perspective, the findings have clear implications for organizations aiming to foster creativity. First, managers should recognize that simply offering some incentives and support mechanisms to employees may not be enough; organizations must also cultivate a culture of trust and encourage psychological ownership to amplify the effects of this support. This can be achieved by ensuring open communication, transparency in decision-making, and involving employees in meaningful ways in organizational processes. Building a high-trust environment and providing opportunities for employees to feel ownership over their work will likely result in higher levels of creativity and innovation. These strategies can be particularly useful for organizations seeking to leverage employee creativity as a source of competitive advantage.

5.3. Future Research Directions

While this study provides valuable insights, several avenues for future research could further explore the complexities of the POS-ECB relationship. Longitudinal studies would provide a more detailed understanding of how the relationships between POS, ECB, TiO, and PO evolve over time. Tracking changes in these variables could reveal more about the long-term impact of organizational support on creativity, particularly as trust and ownership dynamics shift in response to organizational changes or leadership turnover. Cross-cultural comparisons could provide a richer understanding of how different cultural contexts

influence the POS-ECB dynamic. This study was conducted within Turkish companies, where organizational structures and cultural values may differ significantly from other regions. Replicating this research in different countries or industries would enhance the generalizability of the findings and provide insights into how organizational support influences creativity across various settings. Exploring additional moderating variables could further refine the model. For instance, leadership styles, employee engagement, and organizational culture are likely to play significant roles in shaping the effectiveness of POS. Investigating these factors could offer a more comprehensive understanding of how organizational support interacts with other organizational dynamics to drive creativity. Finally, qualitative research could complement these quantitative findings by providing a more nuanced view of how employees perceive organizational support, trust, and ownership in their day-to-day work. Interviews or case studies would allow researchers to explore the subjective experiences of employees and how these experiences influence their creative behaviors.

5.4. Limitations

Despite the valuable insights provided by this study, several limitations should be noted.

1. **Geographic and cultural limitations:** The sample was drawn from Turkish companies, which may limit the generalizability of the findings to other regions or cultural contexts. Organizational dynamics and perceptions of support may vary based on cultural norms and practices, so future research should examine these relationships in more diverse settings to enhance external validity.
2. **Cross-sectional design:** This study utilized a cross-sectional research design, capturing a single point in time. While the results demonstrate significant relationships, they do not provide insight into how these relationships change or develop over time. Longitudinal studies would be beneficial to explore causal relationships more thoroughly.
3. **Sample size and organizational context:** The study focused predominantly on medium to large organizations. While the findings are applicable to such enterprises, they may not fully capture the dynamics of smaller organizations or start-ups, where hierarchical structures and resource constraints may shape the POS-ECB relationship differently. Future studies should consider these variations by

exploring the model in smaller, more agile organizations.

4. **Unexplored moderators:** Although this study focused on TiO and PO as moderators, other variables may also play significant roles in the POS-ECB relationship. For instance, factors like organizational culture, leadership styles, and work engagement were not explored in this study but could offer valuable insights if included in future research.
5. **Small effect sizes:** The baseline variance explained by POS alone was relatively modest (Adj. $R^2 = 0.025$), highlighting the multifactorial nature of employee creativity. While moderation by TiO and PO improved model fit (Adj. $R^2 = 0.069$ and 0.054 , respectively), future studies should incorporate additional predictors such as leadership style, task characteristics, or climate for innovation to achieve higher explanatory power.

6. CONCLUSION

This study has provided valuable insights into the dynamics between Perceived Organizational Support (POS) and Employee Creative Behavior (ECB), with particular emphasis on the moderating roles of Trust in Organization (TiO) and Psychological Ownership (PO). The research confirms that POS positively influences employee creativity, aligning with previous literature that

underscores the importance of organizational support in fostering an innovative environment. By examining the moderating effects of trust and ownership, the study offers a more nuanced understanding of the conditions under which organizational support is most effective in enhancing creativity. The findings indicate that POS alone is not always sufficient to maximize creative output; the presence of high levels of trust and psychological ownership are crucial. Specifically, when employees have strong trust in their organization and feel a sense of ownership over their work, the positive relationship between POS and ECB is significantly amplified. This highlights the importance of fostering both a supportive organizational climate and a culture of trust and ownership to fully leverage employee creativity. The study's contributions to the organizational behavior literature are noteworthy, particularly in expanding Social Exchange Theory (SET) by demonstrating that reciprocity between employees and organizations is contingent on the presence of trust and ownership. By integrating these factors as moderators, the research provides a richer understanding of the POS-ECB relationship and contributes to ongoing discussions about how organizations can foster innovation in increasingly complex environments. Accordingly, organizations should not only provide support but also cultivate high levels of trust and psychological ownership, as these contextual conditions appear to unlock the creative returns of support more fully.

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